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"ADAPTIVE INTELLIGENCE": HEURISTIC POTENTIAL OF THE CONCEPT

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Abstract

In the face of rapid change and uncertainty, a person is looking for the ways to keep unchanged what is important to him. Among other means, the productive combination of intelligence and adaptation is discussed. The purpose of this paper is to explore the importance of "adaptive intelligence" concept, the possibilities and ways of working with it. The need for the empirical study of everyday ideas concerning "adaptive intelligence" concept is shown, the design and expected results of the research are described.

Keywords: *intelligence; adaptation; adaptive intelligence; coping; psychosemantic research.*

The issue of adaptation nowadays is widely represented in philosophical, psychological, and sociological scientific papers as well as in media sphere. According to A.G. Asmolov, *discussion of unpredictability, adaptation, and non-adaptation is becoming "intellectual fashion"* (Asmolov, Shekhter, Tchernorizov, 2108, 50). The books about challenging unpredictability, e.g. "Antifragility" by N.N. Taleb, are sold in big numbers. There are new problematic terms in scientific discourse: starting with a familiar "socio-psychological adaptation", and adding "personal adaptive potential" (Maklakov), "non-adaptive activity" (Pertrovskiy), and "pre-adaptation" (Asmolov).

Russian Public Opinion Research Center reports that the end of February 2022, as well as the spring of 2020, were characterized by the rise of anxiety, irritability, and disorientation levels among Russian citizens (Lvov, 2022). Increased due to covid-19 pandemic and the events in Ukraine in February 2022, ambiguity in social sphere lead to the growth of interest to the topics of uncertainty and adaptation not only among scientists but also among population of the country in general.

"A strange world; the world of exploded unpredictability has already come" (Asmolov, Shekhter, Tchernorizov, 2108, 50), in such circumstances the need to describe and analyze adaptive potential seems especially important. *How satisfying are the existing models for adaptation assessment and adaption training techniques? Is it possible to single out a specific range of adaptive abilities that could be assessed, measured, and developed as well as cognitive abilities and intelligence?*

Is the idea of "adaptive intelligence" a possible basis for future research and effective practical training or is it a possible source of more ambiguity in the semantic field of varied kinds of intelligence? The research, the idea of which is described herein, seeks to find the answers to such questions. **The aim** of the research on the adaptive intelligence is to define its value, possibilities and ways to work with it, and determine possible directions of further knowledge development and scientific research on adaptive intelligence.

J. Piaget was one of the first researchers to write about the connection between intelligence and adaptation: *"for us, intelligence is a certain destination, but its beginning lies within sensomotor adaptation in general as well as within the lowest forms of biological adaptation"* (Piaget, 2004, 11). The scientist, in fact, defines intelligence through the adaptive processes of assimilation and accommodation. The level of "intellectuality" of behavior, according to Piaget, can be defined through the complexity and variability of influence trajectories that a subject uses towards objects. Modern authors develop this idea defining the adaptation as the main task of intelligence: search for the decisions in problematic situations and successful acquisition of various activities (Kholodnaya 2022).

For several decades there has been developing the discussion on a common factor of intelligence in general and separate intellectual abilities. However, a certain answer to the question "how many kinds of intelligences are there", has yet not been found (Kholodnaya 2002, 23). The issue has started to expand beyond the field of knowledge of cognitive psychology. In addition to "psychometric" intelligence, H. Eysenck mentions "biological" and "social" intelligence; H. Gardner describes the wide range of independent types of intelligence in his theory of "multiple intelligences" such as musical-rhythmic, linguistic-verbal, logical-mathematical, visual-spatial, bodily-kinesthetic, interpersonal, and intrapersonal ones (Kholodnaya 2002).

Special attention should be paid to the term "emotional intelligence", which was first mentioned in psychological papers in 1960s, and gained popularity in the end of 1990s – the beginning of 2000s due to journalist Daniel Goleman's works. The most widespread theory of emotional intelligence belongs to Mayer, Salovey, and Caruso, who define emotional intelligence as a type of social intelligence, which includes the ability to notice one's own and other people's emotions, differentiate those emotions, and use gathered data to guide one's thoughts and decisions (Salovey, Mayer 1990).

Can we consider it reasonable to include "adaptive intelligence" into the already overwhelmed semantic

field of other “intelligences”? *If any intelligence is responsible for adaptation as well as other functions, then the term “adaptive intelligence” seems abundant. Nevertheless, it is possible to assume there are certain specific abilities to adapt, which spread beyond cognitive features as well as emotional and social intelligence, and are worth to be studied and described separately from aforementioned.*

The notion “intelligence” is much wider than just adaptive skills. It can also include factors, which do not influence adaptive processes directly, but are connected with cognitive activity. Intelligence is not always equal to adaptation, e.g. one can acquire, understand and effectively use knowledge about M. Vrubel’s frescos, but, in most cases, this knowledge will not contribute to their adaptive skills. Knowledge can have such influence only if the environment requires it for one’s survival. Differences between these notions lead to their symbiosis: adaptive intelligence (AI). We hope AI will help to study coping mechanisms from a novel point of view.

It is important to study the term “adaptation” in socio-humanitarian disciplines. This merely biological term at first then has acquired additional meanings in psychology. Some scientists understand *adaptation as the emergence of behavioral models and strategies, which are suitable to existing circumstances; moreover, it is balanced relationship with the environment including social and cultural ones* (Georgievskiy 1989). The most suitable to our research is the term “*individual adaptive potential*” stated by A.G. Maklakov. He gives it the following definition: “an integrative feature, which includes steady combination of individual psychological and personal qualities contributing to effective adaptation” (Maklakov, Sidorova, 2011, 41). As the components of the adaptive potential, the scientist recognized *neuro-psychological stability, one’s self-esteem, feeling of social support, one’s proneness to conflicts, and experience of social communication.*

Psychological adaptation assessment is based on analyzing such factors as life satisfaction, subjective well-being, and the ability to solve problematic issues in social communication (Melnikova 2004). Some

modern Russian researches state the issue of the connection between socio-psychological adaptation and intelligence, but they do not go any further than eliciting and analyzing correlations between the two.

The exact term “*adaptive intelligence*” can be found in the works of R. Sternberg. He defines this notion as the cognitive activity targeted to task-oriented adaptation, choice and formation of the environment; this activity includes the set of skills, attitudes and behaviors based on *creative analytical and practice-oriented thinking and wisdom* (Sternberg, 2021).

It is crucial to further explore the interrelation between semantic fields of the notions “intelligence” and “adaptation” as well as clarify the structure of the skills comprising adaptive intelligence.

We have conducted **the phenomenological analysis** aiming to elicit typical ideas and create a psycho-semantic model of real world, which is in fact underlies the term “adaptive intelligence”.

We have devised the following stages of the research:

a) to gather semantic base necessary to articulate the notion “adaptive intelligence”;

b) to base the research on the empirically extracted data, namely, associations given by several hundreds of respondents, the bearers of commonplace consciousness;

c) use this data instead of the opinions stated by a limited number of researches who offer only their intuitive ideas to discuss the issue in question.

Study process:

1. Primary collection of phenomena, i.e. stories mentioning AI cases in real context. The search is conducted on social media and with the help of offline surveys.

2. Expertise method is used for eliciting particular stories with all necessary features.

3. Comprising relevant AI thesaurus through Google Forms questionnaire.

4. Content analysis of the data received. Frequency analysis.

5. Designing target AI notions using empirical results.

Results.

Categories of everyday consciousness	WEIGHT – frequency
Creativity	317
Positive peer feedback	314
Improvisation, resourcefulness	199
Skills	175
Coping with the pressure from the objective reality	142
Self-control	139
Intelligence	138
Pro-active attitude	137
Energy-efficient distribution of resources	137
Communicative qualities	115
Time control	109
Powerful influence	100
Belief in oneself	94
Analysis of the situation	84
Mastery, fine execution	78
Ability to relate and compromise	70
Positive results, winning	67
Luck	65
Metaphors, similes	44

Figure 1. Discovered categories ranged according to frequency decrease (semantic weight)

Special attention should be paid to coping potential:

- coping with the pressure from the objective reality;
- self-control;
- pro-active attitude;
- energy-efficient distribution of resources;
- belief in oneself;
- positive results, winning.

Mentioned points mean that a bearer of well-developed adaptive intelligence with higher probability can overcome stress pressure.

As for main goal of the research described, discovered constructs can be used for creating needed notions. First drafts of such notions are presented further.

Scientific definition:

Adaptive intelligence (AI) is the ability to take the best possible decisions in the context of inward and outward limitations. Thus, to assess efficacy of a decision it is necessary to understand the subjective reality of a person making this decision.

For educators:

Adaptive intelligence (AI) is the individual ability to go out and beyond any limitations, either personal or cognitive. One should be fitting in existing society and flexible, and yet showing their individuality.

For recipients:

Adaptive intelligence is the ability to find a solution in any situation where no one else has managed to find it.

Characteristics of model setting: 1) relevance of linguistic intuition (being understandable), 2) psycho-technical potential (persuasiveness), 3) rich operationalization (practical usage).

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